

AI Explanations as Boundary Objects: Toward Shared Language in High-Stakes Decision-Making

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Explainable AI (XAI) research increasingly recognises that different stakeholders hold distinct explainability needs, yet much of this work designs explanations for individual groups in isolation. AI-informed decisions in high-stakes domains must flow between parties with asymmetric knowledge, authority, and stakes, and translational breakdowns emerge when explanations are not designed with this communicative chain in mind. As AI systems become more agentic, reasoning and acting across multiple steps rather than producing single outputs, this fragmentation becomes more consequential. Drawing on team cognition, psycholinguistics, and boundary object theory, and grounded in a case study of diagnostic communication, we argue that the language of AI explanations is a foundational design parameter shaping cross-stakeholder understanding, trust, and accountability. We offer three recommendations for reframing explanation design as a consensus-building activity comprising participatory vocabulary development, iterative explanation negotiation, and ongoing governance. We further propose evaluation metrics including interpretive alignment, translational load, and contestability that shift focus from individual comprehension to cross-stakeholder communicative quality. We contend that the central challenge for human-centred XAI may not be making AI more explainable to individuals, but designing explanations that help people explain, deliberate, and decide together.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Heuristic evaluations**; **Collaborative interaction**; *HCI theory, concepts and models*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Explainable AI, Human-centred XAI, Knowledge Translation, Shared Mental Models.

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1 Introduction

The deployment of AI in high-stakes domains carries significant consequences for affected individuals, from inaccurate diagnosis in healthcare [3], to biased sentencing in criminal justice [5], and inequitable educational outcomes [30]. Explainable AI (XAI) has emerged as a key area of research in response [2, 7], with growing calls for human-centred approaches that treat explainability as a sociotechnical challenge rather than a purely technical one [11, 12]. Yet a persistent tension remains between technical transparency and whether an explanation actually enables informed judgement. Recent work argues this gap is not technical but philosophical. XAI conflates transparency with understanding, when explanation must navigate epistemic asymmetries between stakeholders [19]. The emergence of agentic AI systems, which plan, act, and reason across multiple steps rather than producing single outputs, intensifies this challenge. Explanations must now account not only for what a system concluded, but for the trajectory of reasoning through which it arrived there [37].

A growing body of work acknowledges that different stakeholders hold distinct explainability requirements [16, 28, 41], and efforts to operationalise this insight have produced stakeholder-specific design patterns and transparency tools for clinical contexts [38, 39]. However, much of this research treats these perspectives in isolation. In practice, AI-informed decisions, increasingly generated through agentic processes, must flow between parties with asymmetric knowledge, authority, and stakes, and when explanations are not designed for this communicative chain, translational breakdowns emerge. An ethnographic study of algorithmic policing illustrates the extreme of this failure, in which intermediaries relaying predictions to management gradually moved from translation to substitution, replacing the system’s outputs

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with their own judgments [46]. We argue that the need for intermediary translation should be treated as a design failure, not an organisational inevitability.

Recent work within the HCXAI workshop has begun to explore adjacent concerns. Kallina et al. [22] argued that XAI must move beyond serving developers and narrowly defined end-user groups toward accessibility for all of a system’s stakeholders, while Mansi et al. [32] foreground the power dynamics between *decision makers* and *decision subjects*, arguing that shared understanding can be developed through conversation and collaborative design. We build on both contributions to ask: as research moves toward stakeholder-specific explanations, do these distinctions inadvertently exacerbate the communication breakdowns they aim to address? We argue that the field should move beyond optimising clarity for immediate users, toward shared explanatory norms through which AI explanations can function as boundary objects [40], connecting rather than fragmenting understanding across roles. This paper articulates this vision by drawing on team cognition, psycholinguistics, and boundary object theory, grounded in a case study of diagnostic communication in perinatal pathology where we surface the careful communicative labour involved in expert reporting. We offer a set of recommendations for consensus-based explanation design, and propose evaluation metrics that foreground cross-stakeholder communicative quality over individual comprehension, arguing that the shift toward agentic AI demands a corresponding shift in how we conceptualise the audience and purpose of explanation.

2 Aligning Understanding Across Stakeholders

The concept of a *shared mental model* originates in team cognition research, describing the overlapping knowledge structures that enable team members to coordinate actions and interpret situations consistently [9, 35]. Effective teamwork does not require identical understanding, but instead depends on models that are sufficiently *compatible*: structured differently to reflect each member’s role, yet aligned enough to support mutual prediction [21]. This distinction matters for AI systems in high-stakes workflows, where stakeholders will hold different depths of technical understanding but must act coherently on the basis of a system’s outputs. This distinction is especially salient as AI systems become more agentic, generating outputs through multi-step reasoning processes that stakeholders must act on but may only partially observe. Kim et al. [24] illustrated one dimension of this challenge in their model of *agentic interpretability*, where human responses are integral to the explanatory process itself, creating what they term a *human-entangled-in-the-loop* dynamic in which each stakeholder’s understanding is co-produced through their particular interaction rather than derived from a stable, shared output.

Shared understanding is not merely an interface design goal but a sociotechnical construct, emerging from the interactions and communicative norms between people working within a shared system [25]. Ehsan et al.’s [11] concept of *social transparency* reinforces this view, arguing that explainability must extend beyond algorithmic reasoning to encompass who is using a system, why, and under what conditions, since understanding breaks down not solely because of insufficient technical detail but because the relational dimensions of explanation are left unaddressed. Developing such models across professional boundaries is challenging, as even when diverse teams collaborate, they tend to form different mental representations of the same problem based on disciplinary training and professional norms, creating representational gaps that hinder coordination [10]. Star and Griesemer’s [40] concept of *boundary objects* (abstract or concrete artefacts that can adapt to local needs across communities of practice while retaining a common identity) offers a useful lens here. Recent work in Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) reporting has explored this direction, proposing shared artefacts such as glossaries to help stakeholders communicate through familiar, common objects [45]. We build on this thinking and argue that AI explanations should themselves be designed as boundary objects. The explanatory language of a system should be inherently legible across stakeholder groups, rather than

supplemented by separate translational aids. The importance of this is exemplified by Kim et al.'s [24] acknowledgement that conversational explanation may not produce the kind of shared artefact through which multiple stakeholders can reach consensus, underscoring the need for agentic systems to generate explanatory artefacts that can travel across stakeholder groups.

There is strong precedent for this across high-stakes domains. In healthcare, multidisciplinary team meetings provide communicative infrastructure through which differences in expertise become productive rather than divisive [26], enabling each participant to calibrate their understanding against others' perspectives. More broadly, research across aviation [13, 33], emergency services [15], and surgery [17] has consistently shown that structured communication improves performance and reduces errors, and that breakdowns in shared understanding are a well-documented source of adverse outcomes [29]. These findings suggest that the challenge of aligning understanding across stakeholders is not unique to AI, but that XAI has yet to draw meaningfully on this body of knowledge.

3 How Language Shapes, and Breaks, Explanatory Continuity

If shared mental models provide the cognitive infrastructure for cross-stakeholder understanding, then language is the medium through which that infrastructure is built or undermined. Decision science has long shown that framing effects alter interpretation and choice [42], and health literacy research confirms that even small wording differences in patient-facing materials significantly affect comprehension and risk perception [14]. In the context of XAI specifically, Calisto et al. [8] found that calibrating the assertiveness of AI-generated explanations to clinician expertise levels influenced both trust and scrutiny of outputs. Psycholinguistic research on *epistemic markers*, hedges and boosters that signal degrees of certainty [20], provides a useful vocabulary for understanding these effects. Together, this evidence suggests that the tone and register of AI explanations are not stylistic choices but implicit design parameters that shape how outputs are received and acted upon, a concern that only deepens as agentic systems generate explanatory language dynamically, with framing choices compounding across each step of a reasoning chain.

Critically, language matters beyond the point of delivery. In high-stakes settings, explanations are relayed, summarised, and recontextualised as they move between stakeholders. Failures in interprofessional clinical communication are a well-documented source of adverse outcomes, with differences in terminology and communication styles between professionals frequently identified as contributing factors [4, 6, 29]. The same dynamic applies when domain experts must relay AI-informed reasoning to others, rephrasing the system's language into terms their audience can understand. If the explanation must first be interpreted before it can be passed on, fidelity is lost at each step, and small terminological differences between stakeholders can compound into significant divergence.

In agentic workflows, this communicative chain lengthens further as reasoning unfolds across multiple steps, tool calls, and intermediate outputs [37], each of which may need to be communicated or contested by different stakeholders. Leng et al. [27] demonstrate that structuring an agent's reasoning trace into named, auditable steps makes it possible to detect reasoning flaws systematically. We suggest that if such traces were designed using language that maps onto the shared mental models of the stakeholder chain, they could function not only as audit tools but as communicative artefacts through which different parties build and maintain aligned understanding of an agent's reasoning. This reinforces the case for a shared explanatory language that provides common ground without flattening important differences in expertise.

4 Case Study: Diagnostic Communication in Pathology

Pathology offers a compelling illustration of these challenges. The pathology report is a critical communication tool that must serve multiple stakeholders, yet research has shown that up to a third of clinicians do not always understand its contents, with misinterpretation frequently driven by specialist jargon, inconsistent grading systems, and expressions of uncertainty [34]. Our own research in perinatal pathology, involving interviews with specialist pathologists conducted to understand the sociotechnical context prior to designing an AI-supported system, surfaced similar dynamics. Participants described their reporting work as an active process of translation: filtering diagnostically significant findings from considerable noise in the tissue, prioritising these into a hierarchy of clinical relevance, and framing their language around the specific clinical question posed by the referring team. Pathologists emphasised that they write reports not simply to document what they observe, but to give clinicians something actionable to work with, relating findings to the clinical scenario even when the conclusion is that no pathological explanation was found.

What is particularly striking is the careful and dynamic calibration of certainty in this process. Participants described drawing on a shared but informal vocabulary of hedged expressions ("likely", "suggestive of", "in keeping with", "can't exclude") to signal their degree of confidence, adjusting this language case by case based on what the findings warrant. In some instances, observations noted in the report body were deliberately excluded from the final conclusion, recording a concern without committing to a definitive interpretation. This reveals a form of expert communicative labour that is rarely made explicit in XAI design, namely the work of calibrating language not only to convey information accurately, but to shape how confidently a downstream reader should act on it. If AI-generated explanations are to be integrated into workflows like these, they must account for this nuance. A system that presents findings with uniform confidence, or in language that does not map onto the established communicative norms of the domain, risks disrupting the interpretive practices that clinicians already rely on to make sound decisions together.

Work on AI-mediated communication in pathology suggests both the promise and the limits of current approaches. Yang et al. [47] demonstrated that LLMs can translate pathology reports into language accessible to patients, significantly reducing communication time and improving comprehension. However, such translation remains a downstream supplement rather than a design principle, since the explanatory language of the AI system itself is not co-developed with the stakeholders who must act on it. As agentic AI systems enter biomedical workflows with increasing autonomy [1], the question of whose language these systems speak, and whether that language can support shared decision-making across the clinical chain, becomes increasingly urgent.

5 Towards Consensus-Based Explanatory Design

Shared vocabularies developed through structured multi-stakeholder agreement, from initiatives standardising diagnostic reporting practices in medicine [23] to international engineering and health informatics standards [31, 36], have long demonstrated the value of shared vocabulary for reliable cross-stakeholder communication. As AI systems become more agentic, generating explanatory language dynamically rather than from fixed templates, the gap between system-generated vocabulary and stakeholder vocabulary widens, making the need for shared terminology more pressing. However, shared vocabulary in this context does not necessarily mean a fixed lexicon of pre-approved outputs. Rather, as our case study illustrates, it means establishing the conventions, registers, and epistemic markers within which dynamic language generation operates. We argue that XAI should adopt a similar approach, and offer three recommendations for reframing explanation design as a consensus-building activity:

- (1) **Participatory vocabulary development:** Klein et al.'s [25] team sensemaking framework demonstrates that common ground must be actively built rather than assumed, through perspective-taking and iterative reframing. Applying this principle, we recommend that the explanatory vocabulary of a system should be co-developed with its stakeholders, surfacing where terminology diverges across groups and negotiating shared terms and framing conventions. For agentic systems that generate language dynamically, this vocabulary functions less as a glossary and more as a set of generative constraints, comprising agreed conventions for expressing certainty, signalling limitations, and framing actionability that guide how a system communicates. This could be facilitated through structured co-design workshops, Delphi-style consensus processes [18], or collaborative development of concrete boundary objects [45].
- (2) **Iterative explanation negotiation:** Kieft et al. [43, 44] show that shared mental models can be cultivated through structured explanation and negotiation, and that decision support systems can be designed to progressively align the understanding of different users. We recommend that explanation design should follow a similar iterative process, in which stakeholders review and refine prototype explanations to surface interpretive misalignments and converge on formats that maintain fidelity across the stakeholder chain. For agentic systems, this negotiation should extend to the structure and language of reasoning traces, not only final outputs, since stakeholders may need to interpret, relay, or contest intermediate steps in a system's reasoning process. Approaches might include think-aloud comparison tasks across stakeholder groups, scenario-based walkthroughs of how explanations travel between roles, or structured negotiation sessions modelled on Kieft et al.'s preference elicitation methods [43, 44].
- (3) **Participatory governance:** Explanatory needs evolve as systems, regulations, and user populations change, so we recommend that shared explanatory standards require ongoing stewardship rather than one-off design. This could take the form of explainability design boards, akin to research ethics boards, that convene diverse stakeholders to periodically audit, contest, and update a system's explanatory conventions. This is particularly pressing for agentic systems, where reasoning trajectories evolve with use and where social mechanisms such as critique and revision loops and contestability interfaces [37] must be designed into the explanatory infrastructure rather than bolted on after deployment.

To evaluate this approach, we propose five metrics that move beyond individual comprehension toward cross-stakeholder communicative quality:

- (1) **Interpretive alignment:** the degree to which different stakeholders draw consistent, compatible conclusions from the same explanation, measured through structured comparison tasks.
- (2) **Explanatory fidelity:** whether the core meaning of an explanation is preserved as it is communicated from one stakeholder to another, measured by comparing interpretations at each step.
- (3) **Translational load:** the amount of additional interpretation or rephrasing required for one stakeholder to communicate an explanation to another, where lower load indicates better shared legibility.
- (4) **Cross-role interpretability:** whether stakeholders from one role can accurately predict how stakeholders in another role would interpret the same explanation.
- (5) **Contestability:** whether the shared explanatory conventions enable stakeholders, particularly decision subjects, to meaningfully question or challenge AI-informed decisions or agentic reasoning steps using the same language in which those decisions or reasoning steps were communicated.

6 Conclusion

This paper has argued that trustworthy explainability in high-stakes AI systems depends not only on what is explained, but on the language through which explanations are framed, communicated, and understood across stakeholders. Expert communication already involves careful, context-sensitive calibration of language, and AI explanations that fail to account for these established norms risk undermining rather than supporting decision-making. In response, we offered three recommendations that centre explanation design as a participatory, consensus-building activity: co-developing shared explanatory vocabularies with diverse stakeholders, iteratively negotiating explanation formats that maintain fidelity across the stakeholder chain, and establishing governance structures to steward these standards over time. We further proposed evaluation metrics, including interpretive alignment, translational load, and contestability, that shift the focus from individual comprehension to cross-stakeholder communicative quality. While these ideas require empirical validation across domains, we believe they offer a productive reorientation for the field. The shift toward agentic AI systems, which reason, plan, and act across extended trajectories, makes this reorientation more urgent. As AI outputs become less like single predictions and more like unfolding processes, the need for explanatory language that connects rather than fragments stakeholder understanding only grows. Ultimately, we suggest that the central challenge for HCXAI may not be how to make AI systems more explainable to individual users, but how to design explanations that help the people affected by those systems explain, deliberate, and decide together.

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